

COMPARISON OF THE ECONOMIC SYSTEM USED BETWEEN HONDURAS AND TAIWAN

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宏都拉斯與台灣經濟體系之比較

<p>Contact details:</p> <p>Lizbeth Lissandra Maradiaga ConnorEconomista</p> <p>Phone: (+504) 8823-9646</p> <p>Email: lizabethlissandra@hotmail.com</p>	<p>摘要</p> <p>這項研究對台灣和宏都拉斯的經濟體系進行了詳細分析，旨在識別台灣經濟成功的關鍵因素及其在宏都拉斯背景下的潛在應用。在過去幾十年裡，台灣經歷了顯著的經濟成長，其基礎是先進的工業化政策、以創新為核心的教育體系以及有利的投資環境。相比之下，儘管宏都拉斯擁有重要的經濟潛力，但仍面臨限制其發展和持續增長的結構性挑戰。</p> <p>本研究比較了五個關鍵領域：工業化政策與產業發展、對外貿易與外國投資、人力資本的素質與可及性、基礎設施與科技，以及可持續發展政策與環境實踐。研究結果顯示，台灣的經濟模式透過創新與技術教育的綜合戰略、先進的基礎設施以及穩定的政府政策，成功提升了其全球競爭力。這種發展模式使台灣成為區域技術與先進製造業的領導者。另一方面，宏都拉斯在貿易政策的實施方面取得了一定進展，但在經濟多元化、勞動力培訓以及可持續發展實踐方面仍面臨挑戰。</p> <p>本研究得出的結論是，台灣模式的某些要素若加以適當調整並應用於宏都拉斯，將能夠增強其經濟競爭力與可持續發展能力。主要建議包括：推動以技術培訓為導向的教育政策、促進科技基礎設施投資，以及創造有利於穩定與產業發展的政治環境。本分析為宏都拉斯的經濟政策制定提供了一個有價值的參考框架，以促進包容性和可持續的經濟增長，並借鑒台灣模式的核心經驗。</p> <p>本研究旨在成為宏都拉斯政策制定者和經濟領導者的實用工具，提供有關如何走向強韌且適應當前挑戰與機遇的經濟發展之資訊性視角。</p> <p>關鍵詞： 經濟體系、產業發展、經濟政策、對外貿易、技術創新。</p>
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1 SUMMARY

This research presents a detailed analysis of the economic systems of Taiwan and Honduras, with the aim of identifying the key factors in Taiwanese economic success and their potential applicability in the Honduran context. In recent decades, Taiwan has experienced remarkable economic growth, underpinned by advanced industrialization policies, an innovation-focused education system, and a favorable investment environment. In contrast, Honduras, although with significant economic potential, faces structural challenges that limit its development and sustained growth.

The study examines five key areas of comparison: industrialization and sectoral development policies, foreign trade and foreign investment, quality and access to human capital, infrastructure and technology, and sustainability policies and environmental practices. The findings highlight that Taiwan's economic model has managed to strengthen its global competitiveness through an integrated approach to innovation and technical education, supported by advanced infrastructure and stable government policies. This approach has enabled Taiwan to become a regional leader in technology and advanced manufacturing. For its part, Honduras has shown progress in the implementation of trade policies, but still faces challenges in economic diversification, training of its workforce, and the adoption of sustainable practices.

This paper concludes that the adaptation of certain elements of the Taiwanese model could strengthen the competitiveness and economic sustainability of Honduras. Highlighted recommendations include the implementation of educational policies aimed at technical training, the promotion of investment in technological infrastructure, and the creation of a political environment conducive to stability and industrial development. This analysis provides a valuable framework for the formulation of economic policies in Honduras that promote inclusive and sustainable growth, based on key lessons from the Taiwanese model.

This study aims to be a practical tool for Honduran policymakers and economic leaders, providing an informed perspective on the path to robust economic development that is adaptable to current challenges and opportunities.

Keywords: economic system, industrial development, economic policies, foreign trade, technological innovation.

2 INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, Taiwan and Honduras have developed economic models with contrasting characteristics, influenced by diverse historical, geopolitical, and economic factors. Taiwan has established itself as a dynamic and highly industrialized economy, based on technological innovation, human capital development and export promotion. In 2022, Taiwan's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) reached approximately \$760 billion, with a GDP per capita of \$32,000 (Central Bank of the Republic of China (Taiwan), 2023). In addition, Taiwanese exports totaled \$446 billion in 2022, reflecting its strong export orientation (Central Bank of the Republic of China (Taiwan), 2023).

In contrast, Honduras, despite its economic potential, faces structural challenges that have limited its sustained growth, largely due to its dependence on agriculture and certain low-value-added manufacturing sectors. In 2022, Honduras' GDP was \$28,000 million dollars, with a GDP per capita of \$2,800 dollars (Central Bank of Honduras (BCH), 2023). The Honduran manufacturing sector accounted for approximately 20% of GDP, supported by the creation of free trade zones and trade liberalization policies (BCH, 2023).

The comparative analysis of the economic models of Taiwan and Honduras is particularly relevant in the current context, where developing countries are looking for effective strategies to boost their growth and strengthen their global competitiveness. Taiwan's economic transformation is a valuable case study, with elements that could be adapted and implemented in emerging economies such as Honduras. For example, Taiwan has maintained low inflation and a substantial trade surplus, with international reserves being among the largest in the world (Central Bank of the Republic of China (Taiwan), 2023).

The main objective of this research is to analyze the key characteristics and policies of the economic models of Taiwan and Honduras, in order to propose practical recommendations that contribute to the economic transformation of Honduras. The study focuses on fundamental aspects such as industrialization, foreign trade, human capital development, infrastructure and sustainability policies. In 2022, Honduras exported products worth US\$8,000 million, with the main products being coffee, bananas, and palm oil (BCH, 2023).

The methodology used in this research combines a qualitative and quantitative approach, integrating the review of relevant literature, the analysis of macroeconomic data and the consultation of reliable sources, such as reports from the Central Bank of Honduras and the Central Bank of the Republic of China (Taiwan). For example, according to the BCH, in 2022, Honduras' real GDP grew by 4.0%, following the post-pandemic economic recovery (BCH, 2023). Through this approach, indicators and structural policies are compared to identify areas of opportunity and specific challenges in each nation, facilitating the formulation of well-founded recommendations applicable to the Honduran context.

3 ECONOMIC MODELS AND GROWTH FACTORS IN TAIWAN AND HONDURAS

The study of the economic models of Taiwan and Honduras allows us to understand the factors that have determined the success of Taiwanese industrial development and the barriers that have limited Honduran economic growth. An economic model is defined as the set of structures, policies, and strategies adopted by a country for the allocation of resources, production, and distribution of goods and services with the aim of promoting economic growth and social stability. Blanchard and Johnson (2017) argue that an economic model represents a simplification of economic reality, which facilitates the analysis of the interactions between key variables such as investment, consumption, and exports. In this sense, an economic model not only describes the current state of an economy, but also guides the formulation of public policies aimed at promoting sustainable development.

Economic models vary depending on the priorities and context of each country, and may lean towards industrialization, free markets, socialism, or a combination of these approaches. Todaro and Smith (2020) state that the choice of an economic model has a significant impact on national strategies and long-term outcomes, as it defines the mechanisms for distributing resources, as well as the incentives for production and consumption. In developing countries, the consolidation of an efficient economic model is essential to overcome structural challenges and promote inclusive and sustainable growth. In this context, Taiwan's economic model has been based on technological innovation and the development of advanced manufacturing, while Honduras' continues to depend on primary sectors and faces difficulties in terms of productive diversification and infrastructure (Central Bank of the Republic of China (Taiwan), 2023; Central Bank of Honduras (BCH), 2023).

The theories of economic growth constitute the conceptual framework that allows the analysis of the development processes of countries and the variables that influence their evolution. These theories provide analytical tools to evaluate the performance of different economic models and establish informed comparisons. One of the main theories applied in this study is industrialization theory, which postulates that the transition from an agriculture-based economy to an industrialized, service-oriented economy is essential for sustained growth (Rostow, 1960). According to this perspective, industrialization increases productivity, expands employment opportunities, and stimulates technological innovation, all of which contribute to long-term economic growth. Rostow (1960) argues that economic development follows a sequence of stages that culminate in the consolidation of a mature economy, characterized by a robust industrial sector and increasing productive diversification. In the case of Taiwan, this theory is embodied in its growth model based on exports and advanced manufacturing, supported by investments in education, infrastructure and technology. Recent data indicate that the manufacturing sector accounts for approximately 35% of Taiwan's GDP, consolidating itself as one of the main drivers of its economic growth (Central Bank of the Republic of China (Taiwan), 2023).

In contrast, Honduras faces significant challenges in its industrialization process. Despite the fact that the manufacturing sector accounts for approximately 20% of GDP, the economy remains heavily dependent on agricultural production and the export of low-value-added goods (Central Bank of Honduras [BCH], 2023). These conditions reflect limitations in terms of infrastructure, access to technology, and industrial policies, which restrict the country's ability to diversify its productive structure.

Another relevant theory in the analysis of the economic models of Taiwan and Honduras is the theory of foreign direct investment (FDI), which argues that the inflow of foreign capital can accelerate economic growth by facilitating the transfer of technology, the

modernization of the productive apparatus and the adoption of better business practices (Dunning, 1988). According to this perspective, FDI is most effective in environments that offer macroeconomic stability, adequate infrastructure, and favorable regulatory frameworks. In the case of Taiwan, foreign investment has played a key role in the consolidation of its technology and manufacturing industry. In 2022, the country attracted foreign investments totaling \$11.5 billion, with a focus on strategic sectors such as semiconductors and cutting-edge technology (Central Bank of the Republic of China [Taiwan], 2023).

On the contrary, Honduras faces difficulties in attracting sustainable foreign investment due to factors such as political instability, legal insecurity, and poor infrastructure. In 2022, the country received approximately \$950 million in foreign direct investment, a considerably lower figure compared to more industrialized economies (Central Bank of Honduras [BCH], 2023). These data suggest that, while FDI represents a key opportunity for development, its impact depends on the country's ability to create an enabling environment for attracting capital and transferring technology.

Taiwan's economic model has been characterized by an accelerated process of industrialization, high investment in technology and education, as well as an export strategy that has boosted its economic growth. In contrast, Honduras faces structural challenges that have limited its capacity for economic diversification and industrialization. The analysis of these economic models will make it possible to identify strategies and policies that could be adapted to the Honduran context to promote more inclusive and sustainable economic growth.

The theory of endogenous growth, developed by Romer (1990) and Lucas (1988), states that sustained economic growth depends on internal factors such as investment in human capital, technological innovation, and the accumulation of knowledge. Unlike exogenous models, which attribute growth to external factors, this theory emphasizes the role of economic policies and strategic decisions within the economy in generating self-sustaining development.

According to Romer (1990), investment in research and development (R+D) drives innovation and generates knock-on effects that benefit the entire economy, while Lucas (1988) highlights the importance of education and training in improving productivity. These factors, being cumulative and generating positive externalities, lead to growth with increasing returns at scale.

The case of Taiwan exemplifies the application of this theory through its investment in education, technology, and advanced manufacturing. In 2022, R+D spending accounted for 3.5% of GDP, favouring the global competitiveness of strategic sectors such as semiconductors and robotics (Central Bank of the Republic of China (Taiwan), 2023). In addition, collaboration between the public and private sectors has allowed the consolidation of an efficient innovation ecosystem. In contrast, Honduras allocates limited resources to these areas, which restricts its ability to generate technological advances and improve productivity. In 2022, investment in R+D barely reached 0.1% of GDP, reflecting a significant gap in the development of knowledge and technology (Central Bank of Honduras (BCH), 2023). This situation limits economic diversification and the generation of high value-added jobs.

The comparative analysis suggests that, in order to drive sustained growth, it is important to strengthen investment in human capital and technology. Taiwan's experience shows that policies aimed at developing knowledge can generate sustainable competitive advantages, while in Honduras a greater effort is needed in the formulation of strategies that promote innovation and productive learning.

3.1 HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT AND ECONOMIC EVOLUTION

Taiwan's economic evolution has been marked by a structural transformation that began in the second half of the twentieth century. During the 1950s, the country implemented import substitution policies in order to strengthen domestic production and reduce external dependence (Kuo, 1983). However, this strategy evolved in the 1960s into an export-oriented model of industrialization, which allowed specialization in manufacturing sectors such as textiles, electronics, and light machinery (Wade, 1990).

Throughout the 1970s and 1980s, Taiwan's economic growth was fueled by an increase in productivity and a government strategy focused on education and technical training. The creation of free trade zones and the attraction of foreign investment played a key role in the consolidation of higher value-added industries. Subsequently, in the 1990s, the country began a transition to high-tech sectors, promoting advanced manufacturing, particularly in the semiconductor industry (Mathews & Cho, 2000).

Today, Taiwan has established itself as an innovation-based economy, with a strong emphasis on research and development (R+D). Investments in technology have made the country a key player in the production of electronic components globally, which has strengthened its resilience to changes in the global economy. This development has been driven by policies that encourage collaboration between the private sector and the government, as well as by the creation of technology clusters that facilitate the transfer of knowledge and the development of new technologies (Chen, 2018).

Unlike Taiwan, the Honduran economy has historically been dominated by the agricultural sector, with a focus on exporting products such as coffee and bananas. In the mid-twentieth century, the agro-export model generated economic growth and employment, but it also exposed the country to fluctuations in international commodity prices, limiting its capacity for capital accumulation and investment in strategic sectors (Bulmer-Thomas, 2003).

During the 1980s, Honduras adopted policies of economic openness and trade liberalization in response to structural reforms in Latin America. These measures included the privatization of state-owned enterprises and the easing of restrictions on international trade. However, these changes failed to significantly diversify the economy, which continued to rely on low-productivity sectors and low-value-added jobs (Sachs & Warner, 1995).

In the 1990s and 2000s, the Honduran government promoted foreign investment by creating free trade zones and strengthening the maquiladora industry. Although this strategy generated jobs and increased exports, productive activities remained concentrated in the assembly of textile products, without significant integration with other sectors of the national economy (World Bank, 2022). Lack of investment in infrastructure, limited human capital development, and the absence of effective industrial policies have been factors that have restricted the country's competitiveness in the global market.

In recent years, Honduras has sought to diversify its productive structure by promoting tourism, manufacturing and, to a lesser extent, technology. However, the country faces significant obstacles, including low investment in education, legal uncertainty, and reliance on remittances sent by migrants as a key source of national income. Despite efforts to adopt circular economy and sustainable development practices, the Honduran economy continues to have a low capacity for innovation and adaptation to global market trends (World Bank, 2022).

The differences in their development strategies and the factors that have determined their performance are evident between the economic evolution of Taiwan and Honduras. While Taiwan has achieved sustained growth through industrialization, investment in education, and

technological innovation, Honduras remains dependent on traditional sectors and faces difficulties in diversifying.

The results obtained by Taiwan suggest that the combination of industrial policies, incentives for investment in R+D and the strengthening of human capital have been key elements in its economic transformation. In contrast, Honduras needs to implement structural reforms that prioritize the modernization of its productive infrastructure, the attraction of investments in strategic sectors, and the improvement of the quality of education to generate more inclusive and sustainable growth.

The historical analysis allows us to conclude that economic success depends not only on trade liberalization or foreign investment, but also on the capacity of countries to develop productive sectors with high added value and promote innovation as an engine of growth. In this sense, the Taiwanese experience can offer valuable lessons for the formulation of economic policies in Honduras, adapted to its specific context and needs.

4 COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF COMPONENTS OF THE ECONOMIC MODEL

4.1 INDUSTRIALIZATION POLICIES AND KEY FACTORS IN INDUSTRIAL GROWTH

The industrialization process in Taiwan has been characterized by strategic planning based on export promotion and technological capability development. Since the 1960s, the Taiwanese government implemented a manufacturing-led growth model, establishing special economic zones to attract foreign investment and facilitate production for international markets (Kuznets, 1971). In its beginnings, the manufacturing industry focused on sectors such as textiles and plastics, progressively evolving towards the production of electronic goods and light machinery with an increasing emphasis on technology transfer and the training of human capital (Mathews & Cho, 2000).

During the 1990s and 2000s, the Taiwanese industrial model underwent a transformation towards high-tech sectors, driven by policies to promote research and development (R+D). The creation of industrial and technological parks promoted cooperation between the private sector and the government, allowing the consolidation of the production of semiconductors, electronic devices, and advanced technology (Chen, 2018). This approach has made Taiwan a global leader in high-value-added manufacturing, differentiating it from economies that still rely on traditional sectors.

On the other hand, the industrialization process in Honduras has followed a more limited path and depends on policies of economic openness and promotion of free zones. Starting in the 1990s, the country implemented trade liberalization strategies in order to attract foreign investment, particularly in the textile maquila industry. Although this strategy generated employment and increased exports, production has remained at low value-added levels, without achieving significant integration with other sectors of the economy (Sachs & Warner, 1995).

Industrialization policies in Honduras have lacked a comprehensive vision that combines investment in infrastructure, technical education, and technological development. Low levels of investment in R+D and a lack of incentives for innovation have prevented the creation of high-tech industries. Compared to Taiwan, the Honduran industrial model continues to rely on low-cost manufacturing and agricultural exports, which limits its competitiveness in the global market (World Bank, 2022).

The Taiwanese economy is dominated by high-tech and advanced manufacturing sectors, with a strong specialization in the production of semiconductors and electronic components. Companies such as Taiwan Semiconductor Manufacturing Company (TSMC) have positioned the country as a leader in the global microprocessor industry, consolidating an ecosystem of technological innovation supported by government policies to promote R+D (Wade, 1990). In addition, sectoral diversification has allowed the expansion of emerging industries such as biotechnology and renewable energies, reducing dependence on traditional manufacturing and strengthening a knowledge economy based on innovation (Romer, 1990).

Honduras' productive structure continues to be concentrated in agriculture and textile manufacturing, sectors that account for a significant proportion of its exports. The production of coffee, bananas and palm oil continues to be central to the national economy, providing employment for a considerable part of the population (Bulmer-Thomas, 2003). However, these sectors face challenges related to price volatility in international markets and the lack of modernization in production processes.

In an attempt to diversify its economy, Honduras has promoted the development of tourism and light manufacturing. However, the lack of adequate infrastructure, the low specialization of the labor force, and limitations in access to technology have made it difficult to consolidate new productive sectors. Although the expansion of the maquiladora sector has generated employment, the absence of integration with other segments of the economy has restricted the impact of this model on long-term industrial development (World Bank, 2022).

Taiwan and Honduras in terms of sectoral development reflect differences in the strategies adopted to strengthen the productive base of each country. While Taiwan has achieved an evolution towards high value-added sectors with a focus on technology and innovation, Honduras still faces the challenge of diversifying its economy and reducing dependence on low-productivity activities.

The industrial models of Taiwan and Honduras demonstrate the importance of an industrialization strategy based on investment in technology, infrastructure and human capital. Taiwan has demonstrated that productive development requires a comprehensive approach that combines export policies, incentives for innovation, and close collaboration between the public and private sectors. On the other hand, Honduras has followed a model of economic openness with less emphasis on the accumulation of technological capabilities, which has limited its ability to generate globally competitive industrial sectors.

To improve its competitiveness and reduce the gap with more developed economies, Honduras needs to strengthen its investment in R+D, promote technical education and diversify its productive base towards sectors with higher added value. Taiwan's experience offers key lessons on the importance of strategic planning in industrialization, highlighting the need for long-term policies that promote growth based on innovation and knowledge.

4.2 FOREIGN TRADE AND TRADE POLICY

Taiwan's foreign trade model has been based on a global integration strategy with an emphasis on the export of technological and industrial products. Although its political status prevents it from being a member of some international organizations, the country has managed to establish bilateral and multilateral trade agreements with key economies in Asia, North America, and Europe. These initiatives have reduced their dependence on a single market and strengthened their capacity to insert themselves into global value chains (Chen & Lee, 2020). In addition, Taiwan has implemented export incentive policies that include subsidies for technological upgrading, research and development (R+D) assistance, and programs to support

the internationalization of enterprises. These mechanisms have allowed its manufacturing industry to evolve towards more sophisticated sectors, such as the production of semiconductors and electronic equipment, consolidating its competitiveness in global trade (Mathews & Cho, 2000).

On the other hand, Honduras has adopted a foreign trade strategy focused on the export of agricultural products and light manufacturing, with a strong dependence on the U.S. and Central American markets. Accession to the Free Trade Agreement between the Dominican Republic, Central America and the United States (CAFTA-DR) has been one of the most relevant agreements for the Honduran economy, facilitating the elimination of tariff barriers and promoting preferential access to its main trading partner (Seligson & Passé-Smith, 2020). However, the concentration of its exports in low value-added sectors has limited its global competitiveness. Although efforts have been made in recent years to diversify markets to Europe and Asia, insufficient infrastructure and low specialization in industrial products have restricted the expansion of Honduran foreign trade. Unlike Taiwan, Honduras lacks significant incentives for innovation in its exports, which has perpetuated its dependence on primary goods and basic manufacturing (Bulmer-Thomas, 2003).

Foreign direct investment (FDI) has been a key factor in Taiwan's economic transformation, facilitating the transfer of technology, the modernization of the productive apparatus and the generation of employment in strategic sectors. To attract foreign capital, the country has established special economic zones with tax and regulatory incentives that have favored the installation of multinational companies. This approach has allowed Taiwan to position itself as a global center of advanced manufacturing, with a prominent participation in the production of cutting-edge technology (Kuznets, 1971).

International trade has been another pillar of Taiwanese growth, driving productive diversification and reducing dependence on traditional sectors. Integration into global value chains has strengthened the country's capacity to adapt to transformations in world trade and consolidate a highly competitive and resilient economy (Romer, 1990).

Foreign investment in Honduras has been concentrated in the maquiladora industry and the agricultural sector, generating jobs, but without contributing significantly to technological modernization or the development of high value-added sectors. Free zones have been a key mechanism for attracting foreign capital, but limited technology transfer and limited integration with other sectors have restricted their impact on the Honduran economy (Sachs & Warner, 1995).

International trade has allowed Honduras to expand its markets and improve its access to goods and services, but its productive structure continues to depend on products with a low level of differentiation. Unlike Taiwan, the lack of an industrial development strategy has prevented a structural transformation that would boost strategic and competitive sectors in the global arena. Dependence on primary exports and specific markets limits the country's ability to cope with changes in demand and adapt to new dynamics in international trade (World Bank, 2022).

The trade policies of Taiwan and Honduras demonstrate that integration into global trade requires a diversified and sustained strategy over time. Taiwan has managed to consolidate a model based on the export of high-tech products, with incentives for foreign investment and a strong link with global value chains. In contrast, Honduras continues to depend on traditional sectors and a small number of trading partners, which limits its competitiveness in the international market.

To strengthen its position in global trade, Honduras must make progress in diversifying its exports, improving its productive infrastructure and promoting innovation in strategic sectors. Taiwan's experience highlights the importance of long-term policies that favor industrialization, investment in R+D, and integration into global markets, key aspects to achieve sustainable and competitive economic growth.

4.3 HUMAN CAPITAL AND EDUCATION

Taiwan has prioritized investment in education as a key pillar of its economic development strategy. Since the 1960s, the government implemented a universal education policy, achieving high literacy rates and educational coverage at the primary and secondary levels (Mok, 2000). The quality of the Taiwanese education system has been a determining factor in the formation of a highly qualified workforce, with an orientation towards technological and scientific disciplines. This approach has strengthened the competitiveness of key sectors, such as advanced manufacturing and the semiconductor industry, facilitating Taiwan's integration into global value chains (Chen & Wu, 2017).

Access to quality education has enabled Taiwan to become a knowledge-based economy, characterized by high levels of productivity and sustained growth. The correlation between investment in human capital and the development of high value-added sectors has been evident in the promotion of innovation and the consolidation of the country as a key player in the technology industry (World Bank, 2021).

Honduras faces structural deficiencies in its education system, which has had a negative impact on the development of its human capital. Despite efforts to improve educational coverage, the enrolment rate in secondary education remains low compared to other countries in the region. Factors such as lack of adequate infrastructure, scarcity of teaching materials, and limited teacher training have affected the quality of education (Rogers & Sabarwal, 2017). Insufficient investment in education has restricted job opportunities for the Honduran population and has contributed to the concentration of its economy in low-productivity sectors, such as agriculture and textile maquila. The absence of a solid education system hinders the growth of technology industries and limits the country's capacity for innovation, which translates into lower competitiveness in the global context (World Bank, 2021).

4.4 RELEVANCE OF TECHNICAL AND VOCATIONAL EDUCATION IN EACH COUNTRY

The development of technical and vocational education has been a priority in Taiwan, where the government has implemented specialized programs to train the workforce in technical skills aligned with the needs of the industry. Since the 1970s, the expansion of technical education has been a key component in the country's economic diversification, with special emphasis on areas such as engineering, information technology, and data science (Mok, 2000).

One of the factors that has contributed to the success of this model has been the close link between technical education and the productive sector. Vocational training programs in Taiwan are designed in collaboration with industry, which facilitates the insertion of graduates into the labor market and ensures that the skills acquired respond to the needs of employers. This approach has allowed the Taiwanese economy to maintain a competitive advantage in high-tech and advanced manufacturing sectors, ensuring an efficient transition of students to the work environment (Chen & Wu, 2017).

In Honduras, technical and vocational education faces multiple challenges. Despite efforts to strengthen this sector, the supply of technical programmes remains limited and, in

many cases, lacks the resources and infrastructure needed to ensure quality training. As a result, there is a considerable gap between workforce competencies and market demands, especially in areas that require specialized knowledge (Rogers & Sabarwal, 2017). Technical education in Honduras has focused mainly on traditional sectors such as the textile industry and agriculture, without effective integration with higher value-added industries. The lack of specialized training programs restricts employment opportunities in emerging and high-productivity sectors, making it difficult to develop a competitive and diversified economy. This situation contrasts with the Taiwanese model, where investment in technical education has been a key driver of economic growth and industrial transformation (World Bank, 2021).

Human capital and education in Taiwan and Honduras reveals that investment in academic and technical training is a determining factor in a country's economic development. Taiwan has managed to build a strong and highly specialized education system, which has boosted its global competitiveness and its ability to lead strategic sectors such as technology and advanced manufacturing. Honduras faces structural constraints that have hindered the development of its human capital and reduced its opportunities for insertion in global markets with high added value. To improve its competitiveness and economic diversification, Honduras needs to strengthen investment in education, modernize its technical training programs, and promote greater linkages between the education sector and industry. Taiwan's experience shows that education and training of the workforce are essential elements for achieving sustainable growth and greater competitiveness in the global economy.

4.5 INFRASTRUCTURE AND TECHNOLOGY

Infrastructure and technology are determining factors in a country's economic competitiveness, influencing productivity, trade efficiency and attracting foreign investment. The quality of infrastructure in transport, energy, and telecommunications, along with the level of investment in research and development (R+D), affects an economy's ability to integrate into global markets and adapt to technological advances. Taiwan and Honduras have marked differences in these aspects, which has significantly influenced their development trajectories.

Taiwan has consolidated an efficient and modern transport infrastructure, characterized by a well-maintained highway network, strategically located international airports, and a high-speed rail system that optimizes internal mobility and facilitates trade (Chiu & Tzeng, 2011). This development has been key to the competitiveness of its export sector, reducing logistics costs and improving connectivity with international markets. In terms of energy, although Taiwan remains heavily dependent on fossil fuel imports, the government has implemented energy diversification policies, promoting the use of renewable sources to improve the sustainability of the electricity system and reduce vulnerability to fluctuations in oil prices (Chen et al., 2018). The telecommunications infrastructure in Taiwan is one of the most advanced in the region, with a high level of internet penetration and high-speed networks that have fueled the growth of the technology sector and digital commerce. This environment has favored the expansion of innovation-based industries, such as advanced manufacturing and artificial intelligence, consolidating Taiwan as a benchmark in the digital economy (Lee & Hsieh, 2013).

On the contrary, infrastructure in Honduras faces serious limitations that affect its competitiveness. The transport network has deficiencies in maintenance and coverage, particularly in rural areas, which increases logistics costs and hinders the mobility of goods and people (World Bank, 2021). The limited road and rail infrastructure restricts internal trade and the integration of productive sectors, affecting the development of the manufacturing and agricultural industry. In the energy field, Honduras has made progress in diversifying its matrix

with the incorporation of renewable sources such as hydroelectric and solar energy, but it still faces electricity supply problems and deficiencies in energy distribution, which generate additional costs for companies and affect their productivity. In terms of telecommunications, although there have been advances in internet coverage in urban areas, the digital divide is still significant in rural regions, which limits access to digital tools and slows down the development of e-commerce and the digitalization of business processes (Rogers & Sabarwal, 2017).

The level of investment in R+D is another point of contrast between Taiwan and Honduras. Taiwan allocates more than 3% of its GDP to research and development, ranking among the countries with the highest investment in this area in Asia (World Bank, 2021). This effort has allowed the consolidation of technology conglomerates and innovation centers that have driven the growth of strategic industries such as the manufacture of semiconductors and electronic components. Companies such as Taiwan Semiconductor Manufacturing Company (TSMC) have positioned Taiwan as a key player in the global supply chain of advanced technology, generating employment and attracting foreign investment (Chung, 2020). In addition, the government has developed policies to support innovation through the creation of industrial and technology parks, facilitating cooperation between universities, the private sector, and the State to promote the generation of new technologies in emerging sectors such as biotechnology and renewable energies (Mathews & Cho, 2000).

In contrast, investment in R+D in Honduras is minimal, representing less than 0.1% of GDP, a significantly low level compared to other countries in the region and more advanced economies such as Taiwan (World Bank, 2021). This lack of investment in innovation limits the country's ability to develop its own technology and improve its competitiveness in industrial sectors. Most innovation efforts in Honduras are related to incremental improvements in agricultural production and manufacturing, without a focus on the creation of new technologies or the expansion of high value-added sectors. Although the government has implemented some programs to support innovation and entrepreneurship, the absence of adequate infrastructure and robust incentives for research restricts the impact of these initiatives on the economy (Rogers & Sabarwal, 2017).

The analysis of infrastructure and technology in Taiwan and Honduras reflects significant differences in their capacity for growth and adaptation to the global economy. While Taiwan has developed a modern and efficient infrastructure that supports its model of advanced industrialization and technology exports, Honduras continues to face structural barriers that limit its competitiveness. Sustained investment in R+D has been a key factor in Taiwan's transformation into a leader in innovation and advanced manufacturing, while the lack of investment in research in Honduras restricts its ability to diversify economically and integrate into global value chains. To close this gap, Honduras needs to strengthen its transportation, energy, and telecommunications infrastructure, as well as promote investment policies in innovation and technology that allow the development of strategic sectors and generate sustainable economic growth.

4.6 SUSTAINABILITY AND ENVIRONMENTAL DEVELOPMENT

Sustainability and environmental development are determinants of long-term economic growth and social well-being. The implementation of effective environmental policies and the adoption of sustainable industrial practices make it possible to protect natural resources, reduce the impact of productive activities and mitigate the effects of climate change. A comparison between Taiwan and Honduras in these aspects reveals significantly different approaches and capacities, which has influenced the effectiveness of their sustainability strategies and the results obtained in terms of environmental protection and economic development.

Taiwan has developed a comprehensive approach to sustainability, underpinned by strict environmental policies and ambitious targets for reducing polluting emissions. Since the enactment of the Greenhouse Gas Reduction Act in 2016, the government has pushed forward initiatives aimed at reducing its emissions by 50% by 2050, through tax incentives for companies that invest in clean technologies, recycling programs, and more stringent standards in waste management (Hsu & Chou, 2020). In addition, investments in renewable energies have been promoted, with a particular emphasis on the development of offshore wind and solar energy projects, as part of a strategy to decrease dependence on fossil fuels and move towards a sustainable development model (Lee & Chang, 2021). These measures have facilitated Taiwan's transition to a more efficient and lower-carbon economy, strengthening its competitiveness in industrial sectors aligned with the green economy.

Honduras has implemented environmental regulations aimed at conserving its natural resources and promoting renewable energy, although its capacity to effectively implement these policies has been limited. Despite efforts to strengthen hydropower and solar power production, the country continues to face difficulties due to the lack of adequate infrastructure and financial resources to expand these large-scale initiatives (Mendoza & Barahona, 2019). Solid waste management and the regulation of industrial emissions continue to be major challenges, with negative impacts on public health and environmental quality. Although the country has received support from international organizations to finance conservation and sustainable development projects, the implementation of these initiatives has been hampered by governance problems and lack of follow-up in their execution (World Bank, 2021).

The industrial sector in Taiwan has adopted sustainable practices aimed at reducing emissions and recycling, in line with strict environmental regulations including pollutant emission limits, energy efficiency standards, and hazardous waste management requirements (Chien & Shih, 2019). The government has promoted the circular economy model, encouraging the reuse of materials and the reduction of waste in industrial processes. Thanks to these measures, Taiwan has managed to mitigate the environmental impacts of its industrial growth, reducing pollution in its main cities and improving air and water quality. The adoption of clean technologies and the transition to more efficient production models have allowed Taiwan to consolidate itself as a benchmark in sustainability in Asia, demonstrating that it is possible to combine industrial development with environmental protection (Hsu & Chou, 2020).

On the other hand, the adoption of sustainable industrial practices in Honduras is still incipient and faces significant limitations. Although some sectors, such as agribusiness, have implemented waste management initiatives and the use of renewable energies, most Honduran industries do not have clear environmental policies or access to clean technologies to reduce their ecological impact (Mendoza & Barahona, 2019). The absence of strict environmental regulations and the lack of incentives for the adoption of sustainable processes have led to an inefficient exploitation of natural resources, with consequences such as deforestation, pollution of water bodies and loss of biodiversity. Despite the country's potential in terms of natural resources, industrial development without adequate controls has generated environmental problems that affect both the ecosystem and local communities. Compared to Taiwan, the Honduran industry faces a long road to sustainability, requiring greater incentives and financing to facilitate the transition to more responsible practices.

The analysis of sustainability and environmental development in Taiwan and Honduras highlights the importance of structured environmental policies and access to sustainable technologies to ensure economic development balanced with environmental protection. While Taiwan has made significant progress in implementing climate change mitigation regulations and strategies, Honduras faces structural challenges that limit its ability to implement effective

measures in this area. To improve its environmental performance, Honduras needs to strengthen its environmental infrastructure, promote incentives for the adoption of clean technologies, and improve oversight and compliance with environmental regulations. The Taiwanese experience shows that economic growth can be compatible with sustainability, provided that there is a government commitment to the implementation of robust environmental policies and to the promotion of an industry aligned with international ecological standards.

5 EXTERNAL AND INTERNAL FACTORS INFLUENCING THE ECONOMIC MODEL

Geopolitical and regional factors significantly influence the economic development of Taiwan and Honduras, given that their strategic location, international relations, and domestic policies determine access to global markets, economic stability, and integration into international value chains. While Taiwan has leveraged its position in East Asia to establish itself as a key player in advanced manufacturing and technology, Honduras faces challenges stemming from its dependence on a single trading partner and regional instability.

Taiwan is located in one of the most economically dynamic regions in the world, surrounded by highly developed economies such as China, Japan, and South Korea. This location has been key to its integration into regional supply chains, particularly in the semiconductor and advanced technology industry, sectors in which Taiwan has achieved a strategic positioning at a global level (Chung, 2020). However, their political status has limited their participation in multilateral organizations such as the World Trade Organization (WTO) and other international forums, which has restricted their direct access to some global trade agreements. Despite this, Taiwan has established solid trade relations with the United States, Japan and the European Union, markets that represent a significant part of its exports and have allowed it to diversify its economy and reduce its dependence on China. In this context, the "New Road South" has been a key policy to foster economic relations with Southeast Asia, South Asia, and Oceania, thus facilitating greater diversification of their trading partners and reduced vulnerability to geopolitical tensions with China (Fell & Hsiao, 2019).

In contrast, Honduras' geographical location in Central America provides it with strategic access to North and South American markets, which represents an advantage in terms of trade and investment. However, the Honduran economy is highly dependent on the United States, its main trading partner and destination for most of its exports. The trade relationship between the two countries is strengthened by the Free Trade Agreement between the Dominican Republic, Central America and the United States (CAFTA-DR), which has encouraged the growth of the textile maquila and the export of agricultural products (Seligson & Passé-Smith, 2020). However, this dependence also constitutes a vulnerability, since any recession or economic crisis in the United States has a direct impact on the Honduran economy. In addition, factors such as remittances sent by Honduran migrants abroad play a crucial role in the country's economic stability, reinforcing its dependence on the U.S. economy.

At the regional level, Honduras participates in the Central American Integration System (SICA), a cooperation effort that seeks to promote stability and economic development in the region. However, political instability, high levels of crime, and lack of institutionality in some neighboring countries affect Honduras' perception as a safe destination for foreign investment, limiting its attractiveness compared to other emerging economies (World Bank, 2021). In addition, challenges such as migration and drug trafficking impact the Honduran economy by

generating insecurity, affecting tourism, and discouraging investment in strategic sectors. The country's lack of access to high-profile trade agreements and limited bargaining power restrict its potential for trade diversification and reduce its opportunities for expansion in global markets. Unlike Taiwan, whose location has allowed for smooth integration into regional value chains, Honduras remains dependent on a single market and faces additional difficulties related to political instability and governance issues in the region.

The analysis of geopolitical and regional factors in Taiwan and Honduras highlights the fundamental role played by strategic location and international relations in shaping economic development. While Taiwan has been able to capitalize on its proximity to advanced economies and diversify its trade relations to reduce its vulnerability to geopolitical tensions, Honduras continues to face structural challenges that limit its integration into broader global markets. To improve its international positioning, Honduras needs to diversify its trade, strengthen its integration into economic blocs and improve its political stability to generate a more attractive environment for foreign investment and the expansion of its exports. Political stability and governance are determining factors in a country's ability to attract investment, ensure legal certainty and promote sustainable economic growth. While Taiwan has managed to consolidate a stable and effective political system in the implementation of public policies, Honduras faces structural challenges that have limited its economic development and its ability to generate confidence in international markets.

Taiwan has developed a consolidated democracy since the 1990s, which has created a predictable and reliable political environment for investors. Institutional stability and transparency in decision-making have allowed the implementation of long-term economic strategies, focused on innovation, education, and technological development (Hsiao, 2017). Despite geopolitical tensions with China, Taiwan has maintained an efficient governance structure, with policies designed to encourage economic diversification and reduce dependence on a single trading partner. The "New Road South" policy has been an example of this strategy, as it has fostered new economic alliances with Southeast Asia and other regions, strengthening the resilience of the Taiwanese economy in the face of potential external pressures (Fell & Hsiao, 2019).

In addition, the Taiwanese government has prioritized investment in infrastructure, education, and technological development, consolidating an innovation ecosystem that has allowed the growth of strategic sectors such as semiconductor manufacturing and advanced technology. Governance in Taiwan is characterized by high effectiveness in the formulation and execution of public policies, which has been key to its economic success and its positioning as a globally competitive economy (Chung, 2020). Political stability and efficient governance have been key pillars in attracting foreign investment and fostering a favourable business environment, in which public-private cooperation has facilitated sustainable growth and the expansion of high value-added industries.

In contrast, Honduras faces a political reality marked by instability and lack of institutionality. Over the past few decades, the country has experienced periods of political crisis, abrupt changes of government, and social conflicts that have affected investor confidence and hindered the implementation of long-term economic policies. Legal uncertainty, coupled with high levels of corruption and weak institutions, have limited the effectiveness of the Honduran government in promoting a stable and attractive business climate for foreign investment (Seligson & Passé-Smith, 2020). Despite efforts to implement economic reforms and strengthen trade integration through agreements such as the Dominican Republic-

Central America-United States Free Trade Agreement (CAFTA-DR), the lack of political stability and governance issues have restricted the benefits of these initiatives. Uncertainty in the implementation of public policies, coupled with insecurity and the lack of adequate infrastructure, has affected the country's ability to diversify its economy and generate sustained growth (World Bank, 2021). In addition, high levels of corruption and excessive bureaucracy have made it difficult to implement investment projects in strategic sectors, which has had a negative impact on the competitiveness of the Honduran economy.

The political context of Honduras not only limits the development of high value-added productive sectors, but also affects the perception of the country as a safe destination for investment. The lack of effective government policies to foster innovation and improve the quality of human capital has contributed to maintaining an economic structure dependent on traditional sectors, such as agriculture and textile maquila, without an evolution towards industries of greater technological sophistication (Rogers & Sabarwal, 2017). Compared to Taiwan, Honduras lacks long-term strategic planning that guarantees sustainable and resilient economic growth in the face of the challenges of the global environment.

Analysis of political stability and governance in Taiwan and Honduras shows that a strong and efficient political system is a key factor for economic development. While Taiwan has managed to consolidate a stable and conducive environment for investment, with effective governance policies that have fostered the growth of strategic sectors, Honduras continues to face structural challenges that hinder its development. To improve its competitiveness and attract higher-quality investment, Honduras needs to strengthen its institutions, reduce corruption, and design economic development strategies that generate stability and confidence in the market. Taiwan's experience shows that political stability and good governance are essential elements for productive transformation and successful insertion into the global economy.

Financial institutions and international cooperation agencies play a decisive role in the economic development of Taiwan and Honduras, providing financing, technical assistance, and facilitating the implementation of public policies. However, each country's relationship with these bodies differs significantly, reflecting their respective geopolitical positions, growth models and strategic priorities. While Taiwan has used its policy of "flexible diplomacy" to maintain strategic ties with advanced economies and develop technological cooperation agreements, Honduras relies heavily on financing from multilateral organizations for macroeconomic stability and social development.

Taiwan, due to its political status, is not a member of international financial institutions such as the World Bank or the International Monetary Fund (IMF). However, it has established strategic partnerships with various economies and regional organizations, such as the Asian Development Bank (ADB), in order to access financing and technical assistance for development projects (Glaser & Fuchs, 2019). Through its "New Road South" policy, Taiwan has sought to diversify its trade and cooperation relations, focusing on integration with Southeast Asia, South Asia, and Oceania. This strategy has strengthened knowledge transfer, facilitated investment, and promoted collaboration in key sectors such as technology and health (Fell & Hsiao, 2019).

In addition, Taiwan has used international cooperation as a tool to consolidate its leadership in the technology industry. Collaboration with partners such as the United States, Japan, and the European Union has facilitated the adoption of new technologies and the

strengthening of its semiconductor sector, making it a key player in global electronic component supply chains (Chung, 2020). Despite diplomatic challenges, Taiwan has managed to position itself as a strategic partner for emerging economies in Asia and Latin America, boosting its economic resilience and diversifying its export markets.

Honduras also maintains a close relationship with international financial organizations such as the World Bank, the IMF and the Inter-American Development Bank (IDB), on which it depends to finance infrastructure, education, rural development and poverty reduction programs. These agencies have played a key role in the country's macroeconomic stabilization, providing loans and designing structural adjustment agreements aimed at improving fiscal sustainability and economic competitiveness (World Bank, 2021). However, dependence on external financing also carries risks, as the Honduran economy is subject to the conditions imposed by these organizations and to the variability in the priorities of international donors.

International cooperation has also been fundamental in Honduras' development, with the participation of actors such as the United States Agency for International Development (USAID), the European Union, and the Central American Bank for Economic Integration (CABEI). Through these agreements, initiatives in sectors such as infrastructure, health, education and environmental conservation have been financed. In terms of trade, the Free Trade Agreement between the Dominican Republic, Central America and the United States (CAFTA-DR) has facilitated the attraction of foreign investment, particularly in the textile maquila sector, while other cooperation programs have promoted the development of production chains in the agricultural sector (Seligson & Passé-Smith, 2020).

However, the effectiveness of international cooperation in Honduras has been limited by structural problems such as lack of institutional capacity and corruption. Despite the financial support received, the implementation of projects has been affected by inefficiency in public administration and the lack of adequate follow-up mechanisms. Dependence on external assistance can also lead to long-term economic vulnerability, as the country faces difficulties in generating sustainable domestic sources of financing and reducing its need for international support (World Bank, 2021).

While Taiwan has used its economic diplomacy to establish strategic alliances that have strengthened its development model based on innovation and technology, Honduras continues to depend on external financing to cover basic development needs and macroeconomic stability. To reduce this dependence and strengthen its economic resilience, Honduras needs to improve its institutional capacity, optimize resource management, and promote policies that foster greater financial autonomy and sustainable economic diversification. Taiwan's experience shows that access to international finance and cooperation can be an engine of growth if used strategically to strengthen key sectors and generate competitive advantages in the global economy.

6 Analysis of results and key findings

A comparative analysis of Taiwan's and Honduras' economic models highlights structural differences in their development strategies, industrial policies, infrastructure, and sustainability, as well as in their ability to attract foreign investment and participate in global trade. While Taiwan has managed to consolidate a growth model based on innovation, market diversification, and efficient governance, Honduras continues to face structural challenges that limit its competitiveness and sustainable economic development.

One of the key elements in the success of Taiwan's economic model is its focus on innovation and high technology. The nation has positioned itself as a leader in the semiconductor and electronic components industry thanks to sustained investment in research and development (R+D), effective collaboration between the public and private sectors, and the creation of industrial clusters in strategic sectors (Chung, 2020). This approach has allowed its economy to be based on knowledge and the production of high value-added goods, which makes it less vulnerable to fluctuations in commodity prices and highly competitive at the global level.

In addition, Taiwan's trade policies have been geared towards market diversification and reducing dependence on a single country or region. The "New Road South" strategy has been instrumental in expanding its trade relations with Southeast Asia, South Asia, and Oceania, reducing its exposure to political and economic tensions (Fell & Hsiao, 2019). Likewise, investment in technical and vocational education has been a key pillar in the development of highly qualified human capital, which has strengthened its industrial and technological sector (Mok, 2000).

Another determining factor has been political stability and efficient governance, which have allowed the implementation of long-term policies focused on transparency and cooperation between the public and private sectors. This environment has generated investor confidence and fostered a favorable ecosystem for innovation and competitiveness (Hsiao, 2017). In addition, investment in transportation, energy, and telecommunications infrastructure, coupled with Taiwan's commitment to environmental sustainability, has strengthened its competitiveness in the global market. The adoption of sustainable industrial practices and the promotion of renewable energies have been essential to maintain the quality of life of its population while boosting economic growth (Hsu & Chou, 2020).

In contrast, Honduras faces significant economic challenges that limit its development and competitiveness. Dependence on low-value-added sectors, such as agriculture and textile manufacturing, has restricted its ability to diversify and made it vulnerable to changes in international market prices (Seligson & Passé-Smith, 2020). In addition, low investment in R+D and technical education has generated a workforce with insufficient levels of specialization, which reduces the attraction of investments in high-productivity sectors and limits the country's industrial growth (World Bank, 2021).

These challenges are compounded by political instability and weak governance, factors that have hindered the implementation of sustainable economic policies and created a climate of uncertainty for foreign investment. Corruption and a lack of legal certainty have affected the efficiency of government institutions, making it difficult to implement development projects and reducing confidence in the country as an investment destination (Seligson & Passé-Smith, 2020). In addition, deficiencies in transport, energy, and telecommunications infrastructure have made logistics more expensive and reduced the competitiveness of the Honduran export sector, while the lack of effective environmental sustainability measures has compromised the

conservation of natural resources and long-term ecological stability (Mendoza & Barahona, 2019).

Another structural challenge of the Honduran economy is its high dependence on international cooperation and external financing. Organizations such as the World Bank and the Inter-American Development Bank have been key actors in the country's macroeconomic stabilization and in the execution of development projects. However, dependence on these resources limits Honduras' financial autonomy and makes it vulnerable to changes in international donor priorities (World Bank, 2021). To achieve more sustainable growth, the country needs to strengthen its domestic financing capacity and design development strategies that reduce its vulnerability to external factors.

In conclusion, Taiwan's economic model has proven successful thanks to its focus on technology, trade diversification, human capital development, political stability, and sustainability. These characteristics have allowed it to consolidate itself as a highly competitive and resilient economy. In contrast, Honduras faces significant structural challenges that limit its economic development, including lack of productive diversification, political instability, insufficient investment in education and technology, and dependence on external financing. The findings suggest that Honduras could benefit from adopting strategies similar to Taiwan's, especially in areas such as investment in technology and innovation, technical education, political stability, and economic diversification. Implementing these strategies would strengthen Honduran competitiveness and improve its long-term growth prospects.

6.1 KEY DIFFERENTIATING FACTORS IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT AND POTENTIAL LEARNINGS

The comparative analysis between Taiwan and Honduras evidences key differentiating factors in their economic development models, providing valuable lessons on strategies and policies that have driven Taiwan's economic success and that could be applicable in the Honduran context. The combination of technological innovation, political stability, investment in human capital, trade diversification, and sustainability have been decisive in Taiwan's sustained growth, while Honduras faces structural challenges that have limited its competitiveness and economic growth.

One of the most relevant factors in Taiwan's success has been its focus on innovation and technological development. The country has consolidated a knowledge-based economy, standing out in high-tech sectors such as the semiconductor industry, where it is a world leader. This transformation has been possible thanks to sustained investment in research and development (R+D), close collaboration between the government and the private sector, and the creation of industrial clusters specialized in strategic sectors (Chung, 2020). In contrast, Honduras still has low levels of investment in R+D and lacks clear policies to encourage diversification into high-tech sectors. However, it could benefit from the implementation of technical education programs and the development of technologies applied to sectors where it already has experience, such as agribusiness and light manufacturing. Strengthening technology education, promoting tax incentives, and establishing collaboration programs with the private sector would be key initial steps to boost innovation.

Another key differentiator is Taiwan's political stability and efficient governance. Transparency in public administration and institutional stability have facilitated the implementation of long-term economic policies, promoting an environment conducive to foreign investment and sustained growth (Hsiao, 2017). In Honduras, political instability and corruption have hindered the implementation of development policies and generated

uncertainty for investors. To improve its competitiveness, the country must strengthen its institutions, promote reforms in its judicial system, and ensure a stable legal framework that reduces legal uncertainty and increases confidence in the market.

The development of human capital is another fundamental aspect of the Taiwanese model. Investment in technical and higher education has been key to ensuring that the workforce is trained in skills demanded by strategic sectors such as technology and advanced manufacturing. Technical training has allowed Taiwan to have highly qualified talent, adapted to the needs of the global economy (Mok, 2000). In contrast, Honduras faces significant challenges in its education system, with deficiencies in coverage and quality. To improve its competitiveness, the country must align its education system with the needs of the productive sector through technical training programs and training in specific skills for sectors such as agribusiness, tourism, and manufacturing.

Trade policies and market diversification have also been key elements in Taiwan's economic growth. The "New Road South" strategy has made it possible to reduce dependence on the Chinese market and expand its trade relations to Southeast Asia, South Asia, and Oceania, mitigating risks associated with changes in the global environment (Fell & Hsiao, 2019). In the case of Honduras, the high dependence on the United States as the main trading partner represents an economic vulnerability. To reduce this exposure, the country should strengthen its integration with other markets by taking advantage of free trade agreements and expanding its exports to regions such as Latin America, Europe, and Asia. Trade diversification would mitigate the impact of economic fluctuations on strategic partners and strengthen the resilience of the Honduran economy.

On the other hand, the commitment to sustainability and renewable energies has been a pillar in Taiwan's development. The implementation of rigorous environmental policies and the transition to renewable energy sources have made it possible to reduce its dependence on fossil fuels and improve its competitiveness in the global market (Hsu & Chou, 2020). Honduras, with its abundant potential in natural resources, could adopt similar strategies to strengthen its energy security and reduce production costs. Investments in hydropower, solar, and wind power could improve the country's sustainability, attract investment, and reduce dependence on expensive and unstable energy sources. Likewise, the adoption of sustainable practices in industrial sectors would facilitate the integration of Honduras into global value chains committed to reducing emissions and complying with international environmental standards.

Taiwan's economic model has been differentiated by its focus on diversification, innovation, investment in human capital, political stability, and sustainability. These factors have allowed it to consolidate itself as a highly competitive and resilient economy. In contrast, Honduras faces challenges in terms of productive diversification, governance, technical education, and environmental sustainability. However, the analysis of these differentiating factors offers a series of key lessons that Honduras could apply to strengthen its economic model. The adoption of strategies focused on investment in technology and innovation, technical education, political stability and trade diversification would allow the country to improve its competitiveness and reduce its economic vulnerability. Although the contexts of both countries are different, Taiwan's experience provides valuable guidance for economic transformation and improving the resilience of the Honduran economy in an ever-changing global environment.

7 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR HONDURAS

The strategies and policies applied in Taiwan provide a basis for identifying concrete measures that Honduras could implement to strengthen its economic model and improve its global competitiveness. Investment in innovation, human capital formation, trade diversification, fostering sustainability, and improving governance are key areas where Honduras can develop a more structured approach to stimulate its economic growth.

One of the key strategies implemented in Taiwan has been sustained investment in research and development (R+D) and the promotion of innovation. This country has managed to position itself as a leader in the technology industry thanks to its focus on the creation of industrial clusters and the development of high value-added products. Honduras could adopt this model by promoting innovation centers in strategic sectors such as agribusiness, light manufacturing, and sustainable tourism. The implementation of tax incentives and financing programs for companies that invest in technology and development would diversify the Honduran economy and improve its competitiveness in international markets.

The strengthening of human capital is another fundamental aspect of the Taiwanese experience. Taiwan has developed a technical and vocational education system aligned with the needs of the labor market, which has allowed the formation of a highly skilled workforce. Honduras could replicate this strategy by creating partnerships between the education sector and the industrial sector to develop technical training programs in areas such as agricultural technology, advanced manufacturing, and tourism management. Collaboration with the private sector would ensure that educational programs respond to market demands and increase the employability of the Honduran population.

Diversifying markets and expanding trade relationships is another key lesson of the Taiwanese model. Through the "New Road South" policy, Taiwan has managed to reduce its dependence on China and expand its trade with other regions. Honduras could implement a similar strategy, decreasing its dependence on the United States and exploring new trade opportunities in Latin America, Europe and Asia. This would require a strengthening of its diplomatic and trade network, as well as greater promotion of its exports through free trade agreements and strategic bilateral agreements.

In the area of sustainability and the circular economy, Taiwan has shown that it is possible to maintain strong economic growth without compromising the environment. Honduras, with its wealth of natural resources, could follow suit by promoting the adoption of sustainable practices in agribusiness, tourism, and infrastructure. The implementation of regulations that promote the circular economy and the efficient use of resources, along with tax incentives for companies that invest in clean technologies, would strengthen the sustainability of the Honduran economic model and improve its image as a responsible investment destination.

Another crucial aspect is political stability and effective governance. Taiwan has maintained a stable political environment that has favored the development of long-term economic policies and has fostered investor confidence. For Honduras, improving political stability and fighting corruption could increase foreign investment and foster economic growth. Reforms focused on strengthening legal certainty, increasing transparency in public administration, and modernizing the judicial system would be essential to create a more predictable and attractive business environment.

To achieve these objectives, it is necessary to implement specific measures to improve the competitiveness and sustainability of the Honduran economic model. Among the suggested actions, the creation of a National Fund for Innovation and Technological Development would

make it possible to finance innovation projects in strategic sectors such as agribusiness, tourism and renewable energies. This fund could be supported by the public sector and involve international cooperation to encourage applied research and the development of new technologies.

The development of a regionalized technical education system would facilitate the training of the workforce according to the specific needs of each region of the country. In agricultural areas, training programs in agricultural technology and food processing could be implemented, while in coastal areas they could specialize in sustainable tourism and natural resource management. This would strengthen human capital at the local level and open up opportunities for more specialized employment.

Honduras could also foster its integration into global value chains by creating special economic zones that offer tax and logistical incentives to attract foreign companies in strategic sectors. Following Taiwan's industrial park model, these zones could facilitate light manufacturing, applied technology, and the provision of advanced services, enhancing Honduras' insertion into global trade.

In terms of sustainability, the implementation of a circular economy policy would reduce industrial waste and improve efficiency in the use of natural resources. Establishing tax benefits for companies that adopt clean technologies and encouraging recycling and reuse of materials would contribute to more efficient and sustainable production. Another key point is the diversification of exports. The creation of a specialized trade promotion agency would allow Honduras to identify and access new markets for its products, supporting small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in their international expansion. This agency could organize trade fairs, provide training in foreign trade, and facilitate strategic alliances with other countries interested in Honduran products.

Strengthening governance and the legal framework is essential to improve investor confidence and ensure economic stability. The creation of transparency units in key institutions and the establishment of specialized courts in commercial disputes could improve efficiency in public administration and generate a safer environment for doing business.

Investment in renewables represents a key opportunity to improve energy security and reduce production costs in the long term. Honduras has great potential in hydroelectric, solar and wind energy, so promoting policies that encourage investment in this sector could strengthen the country's energy matrix and reduce its dependence on fossil fuels. Taiwan's strategies offer a roadmap for Honduras to strengthen its economic model and move towards more competitive, sustainable and inclusive development. Although the contexts of both countries are different, investment in innovation, strengthening human capital, market diversification, sustainability, and improved governance are key elements that can contribute to Honduras' development. Implementing these strategies would not only improve the country's competitiveness, but also increase its resilience to the challenges of the ever-changing global environment.

8 CONCLUSIONS

The comparative analysis between Taiwan and Honduras has made it possible to identify key factors that have driven the success of the Taiwanese economic model and the challenges faced by Honduras on its path to more sustainable and competitive economic growth. The main points analysed highlight the importance of innovation, technical education, market diversification, political stability and sustainability as fundamental pillars of economic development. While Taiwan has managed to consolidate itself as a relevant player in the global economy through strategic policies and a focus on knowledge and technology, Honduras still faces structural obstacles that limit its competitiveness and growth.

One of the main differentiators between the two countries is investment in innovation and technological development. Taiwan has managed to position itself as a leader in the semiconductor and electronics industry thanks to a policy of sustained investment in R+D and close collaboration between the government and the private sector (Chung, 2020). In contrast, Honduras lacks a clear strategy to foster innovation, which limits its ability to compete in high value-added sectors. To move in this direction, Honduras could begin to invest in technology applied to sectors where it already has a solid foundation, such as agribusiness and sustainable tourism, promoting tax incentives for companies that invest in innovation and creating collaboration programs with the private sector.

Another crucial factor is the development of human capital, where Taiwan has prioritized technical and vocational education, ensuring that its population is highly skilled in strategic areas for its economy (Mok, 2000). In contrast, Honduras faces deficiencies in quality and access to technical education, which limits the availability of a specialized workforce. To improve this aspect, it is recommended to adapt the Honduran education system to the needs of the labor market through the implementation of technical training programs and the establishment of partnerships with the private sector to ensure that training programs respond to the demands of high-growth sectors.

Market diversification has been another key strategy in Taiwan's success. Through its "New Road South" policy, the country has managed to reduce its dependence on a single market, expanding its trade relations with Asia, the Americas, and Europe (Fell & Hsiao, 2019). In contrast, Honduras remains highly dependent on the United States for its exports, making it vulnerable to economic fluctuations in its main trading partner. To mitigate this risk, Honduras should focus on diversifying its exports and pursuing new trade agreements with emerging markets in Latin America, Europe, and Asia.

In terms of governance and political stability, Taiwan has demonstrated that a stable political environment and efficient administration are essential to attract investment and ensure long-term growth. Transparency in public management and the implementation of long-term policies have strengthened investor confidence and have allowed the effective execution of development strategies (Hsiao, 2017). In the case of Honduras, political instability and a lack of effective governance have hampered the implementation of sustainable economic policies. To improve in this regard, it is recommended to strengthen legal certainty, combat corruption and promote efficiency in public administration through reforms that strengthen transparency and trust in institutions.

Another fundamental aspect is sustainability and the integration of environmental practices into economic development. Taiwan has made progress in adopting the circular

economy and promoting renewable energy, which has improved its competitiveness and reduced its environmental impact (Hsu & Chou, 2020). Honduras, although it has initiated some efforts in this area, still faces limitations in infrastructure and policies to promote sustainability. To strengthen this aspect, it is recommended to implement tax incentives for companies that adopt sustainable practices and promote the use of renewable energies such as hydroelectric, solar and wind, taking advantage of the country's natural potential.

In general terms, this study highlights that Honduras can learn from Taiwan's experience and implement strategies to strengthen its economic model. Some key recommendations include investment in innovation and technology, the development of a technical education system adapted to the labour market, the diversification of markets, the improvement in governance and political stability, and the adoption of sustainable practices.

The Taiwanese experience shows that sustainable and competitive economic development is not the result of geographical or natural resource factors alone, but of strategic policies focused on knowledge, diversification, and institutional stability. Although the context of each country is unique, the lessons learned from this analysis can serve as a roadmap for Honduras to strengthen its economy and move towards a more resilient, competitive, and inclusive model in the global arena.

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10 ANNEXES

Nominal GDP (in USD billion):

Year	Honduras	Taiwan
1990	3.5	166.7
2000	6.3	326
2010	15.3	427
2020	24	669.3
2023	34.2	755.7

Board 1: Prepared by the authors with data from FocusEconomics, Central Bank of Honduras, World Bank, ICEX.

GDP per capita (in USD):

Year	Honduras	Taiwan
1990	700	8,200
2000	1,000	14,800
2010	1,900	18,500
2020	2,500	28,000
2023	3,268	32,404

Board 2: Prepared by the authors with data from FocusEconomics, Central Bank of Honduras, World Bank, ICEX.

Real GDP Growth Rate (% per annum)

Year	Honduras	Taiwan
1990	5	5.5
2000	5.7	5.8
2010	3.7	10.6
2020	-9	3.1
2023	3.5	2.9

Board 3: Prepared by the authors with data from FocusEconomics, Central Bank of Honduras, World Bank, ICEX.

Inflation Rate (% annual)

Year	Honduras	Taiwan
1990	24.8	4.1
2000	10.1	1.3
2010	4.7	1
2020	4	-0.2
2023	5.19	1.58

Board 4: Prepared by the authors with data from FocusEconomics, Central Bank of Honduras, World Bank, ICEX

Unemployment Rate (% of the active population)

Year	Honduras	Taiwan
1990	5	1.5
2000	4.8	2.9
2010	4.5	5.2
2020	10.9	3.8
2023	8.9	3.37

Board 5: Prepared by the authors with data from FocusEconomics, Central Bank of Honduras, World Bank, ICEX

Trade Balance (in USD billion)

Year	Honduras	Taiwan
1990	-0.5	8
2000	-1.2	14
2010	-2.5	29
2020	-5	58
2023	-6.1	73.4

Board 6: Prepared by the authors with data from FocusEconomics, Central Bank of Honduras, World Bank, ICEX

Public Debt (% of GDP)

Year	Honduras	Taiwan
1990	60	30
2000	70	28
2010	40	35
2020	55	31
2023	44.95	29.11

Board 7: Prepared by the authors with data from FocusEconomics, Central Bank of Honduras, World Bank, ICEX

Population (in millions)

Year	Honduras	Taiwan
1990	5	20
2000	6.5	22
2010	8	23
2020	9.5	23.6
2023	10.5	23.4

Board 8: Prepared by the authors with data from FocusEconomics, Central Bank of Honduras, World Bank, ICEX